

Kidnapping as an Emerging Social Crime in Nigeria: Implications for National Security

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Abstract

The significant impact of kidnapping and other associated crimes is becoming worrisome and perplexing and not only to Nigerians but to the international community. This has heightened the fear of foreigners especially international investors, thereby threatening the foundation of economic development. However, the precarious state of kidnapping and other social crimes in contemporary Nigeria have assumed unimaginable dimension in recent times following the increase in kidnapping for ransom, Boko-Haram terrorists' and bandits' attacks on innocent Nigerians leading to loss of many lives and properties. This paper examined the state of kidnapping, types causes, consequences or effects, and measures undertaken by government to tackle the menace. The paper also adopted economic theory and concluded that security agencies and the general public should be more proactive in curbing the prevalence of the phenomenon. The paper also recommended practical ways to curb or end kidnapping in Nigeria, to include youth empowerment, ensure affairs and better harnessed equitable distribution of resources of the country in order to promote national unity.

Keywords: Kidnapping, social crime, and national security

Introduction

Kidnapping is a major problem in Nigeria in the early 21st century. Kidnapping by bandits and insurgents is among the biggest organized or gang crime in Nigeria and become a national security threat or challenge. Kidnapping as a crime phenomenon is not something that started in recent years. It is as old as the human race. Kidnapping is a crime that is endangering the life of people. This is evident whereby individuals are abducted every day for political or economic gains by the perpetrators of such crime. Kidnapping is seen as lucrative business and the shortest means to wealth by those involved in this crime. The current wave of abductions across the country makes every person a potential target regardless of social class or economic status unlike political kidnapping which started in the Nigeria's oil-rich Nigeria Delta region in the early 2000s and the one by Jihadist terror group, Boko Haram in Nigeria's northeast and northwest that began in 2009 when the conflict there started.

In the Niger Delta, agitators took expatriates working with multinational oil giant's hostage to force oil companies operating there to carry out community development projects for the benefit of the host communities or force government into negotiations for more of economic benefits accruing to the federal treasurer for the region. Abductions by Boko Haram terrorist is to further its agenda, recruit fighters, instill fear, gain more international popularity and force the government to negotiate with it for ransom which is one of the means of generating funds for its terrorist operations. Boko Haram has committed several mass kidnappings of students. Their 2014 kidnapping of over 250 teenage girls from a secondary school in Chibok, Borno state, was one of the talks about. Today the rapid spread of kidnapping has become alarming not only in Nigeria but in other countries across the globe. The prevalent rate of kidnapping in Nigeria is worrisome as almost everyone is affected by it directly or indirectly. Kidnapping cuts across every nook and cranny of Nigeria: places of worship, markets, schools, homes, highways,

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farms, recreational centres, and hotels are not left out. The current security challenges in the country can be understood against existing evidence that even government officials, traditional rulers, wealthy/business men are not spared. (Chidi, 2014 as cited in Dangiwa 2019). Thus, this portrays a great sense of concern regarding kidnapping in the country. Kidnapping has become an everyday event in Nigeria, as it is widespread and cuts across the country. It is booming in the country because perpetrators of the heinous crime continue to communicate with the family members of the victim and the police sometimes cannot locate the kidnappers.

Kidnapping of all sort and manner has gained momentum due to the monetary benefit/gain of the act and almost has left everyone in fear because one might not know who the next victim could be. As mentioned earlier the rich oil regions of the Niger Delta have witnessed this phenomenon on a large scale with the targets being mostly expatriates and Nigerians in the oil business. The kidnapping today has become one of the contemporary social problems in Nigeria, as it has spread almost all over the country extending to places as far as Kano, Katsina, Zamfara, Niger, Borno, Kaduna, Kebbi, Sokoto, Nassarawa States to mention but a few. Also, South-East, South-West and South-South of the country have become known as the kidnappers' den (Sanyaolu, 2009).

Conceptualization of Kidnapping

Kidnapping is a criminal offense consisting of the unlawful taking and carrying a way of a person by force or fraud or the unlawful seizure and detention of a person against his will. In earlier times kidnapping meant carrying a person away to another country for involuntary servitude, to expose him to the commission of further criminal act against his person, or to obtain ransom for his safe release. More recently kidnapping for the purpose of extortion has become a tactic of political revolutionaries or terrorists seeking concessions from a government. Kidnapping can also be defined as the act of seizing and detaining or carrying away a person by unlawful force or by fraud and often with a demand for collecting ransom. (Uzorma and Nwanegbo-Ben 2012). It involves taking a person from their family forcefully without their consent with the motive of holding the person as a hostage and earning a profit from their family. In this regard kidnapping could be for a number of reasons, such as getting monetary reward or getting some sort of benefits from the victim. It is usually done for a motive or for oppressive intentions, the most common of which is extorting money from the family of the victim in the form of ransom for freedom and continual living. Based on this observation one finds in kidnapping cognate terms like capturing, hostage-taking, abduction, hijacking, withholding to mention but a few.

As a crime against humanity, kidnapping is a deviant and unwanted behaviour that is intended to harm both the victim and his family members to create tension within a society. Kidnapping as an organised crime is better noticed when a victim's relations are bringing the ransom. This shows how the perpetrators of the crime are organized so as to carry out their act of criminality. Moreover, this is evident that kidnapping in Nigeria is well organized and involves a network of professionals that are performing different tasks for the survival of their victims (Ugwuleb 2011).

Types of kidnapping in Nigeria

As kidnapping is alarming and becoming a threat to national security in Nigeria the following are identified as types: **Basic Kidnapping:** - By far the most common form of kidnapping, this can be accomplished in most parts of the world with minimal preparation with a relatively low risk of failure. Kidnappers will generally target local businessman or their families, those regarded as being "well-off" without having sufficient resources to spend a great deal of money on security precautions. The kidnappers' goal is a fast, easy, pay off- Generally, the ransoms requested are relatively easy for the victim's family or company to obtain. **High-net-worth Individual Kidnapping:** - Generally the intended target is studied for some time prior to the actual kidnapping, allowing the perpetrators to gather intelligence on security procedures and personal habits. After the victim has been taken his or her family or employer is contacted with the ransom demand. Generally, a negotiation process occurs as most of these incidents are perpetrated by experienced kidnap gangs, the victims is generally released if ransom is paid. As high net-worth individuals become increasingly security-conscious, this type of kidnapping has been on the decline in recent years in favour of less involved kidnappings with smaller, but easier to obtain pay off.

Tiger Kidnapping: - A crime involving a hostage taking in order to force the victim to commit or assist in a theft. The hostage or hostages is or are held as until the victim has met the demands of the criminals. All of the victims work in a location where cash is being handled, such as banks, post-office, currency exchange firms to mention but a few.

Express Kidnapping: - the victim is abducted, then forced to withdraw their own ransom from a bank or ATM. If all goes well the victim is released after wards, generally after having been relieved of all valuables on their persons (and occasionally in their residence). This type of kidnapping is popular in urban areas, due to the prolific ATM. In some cases, this will develop

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into a standard kidnapping, with further ransom demanded of the family or employer. In other cases, the victim is held overnight to get withdrawal limit.

Virtual Kidnapping: - A virtual kidnapping is more a scam than an actual kidnapping. The perpetrators will wait until their target is unreachable (visiting an area with no cellular coverage for example), then will contact the target's family or company, claiming they have kidnapped the target eventually returns unaware that anything untoward has occurred. Due to the need for haste the ransoms demanded are generally relatively modest. Another common technique is to call the target pretending to be a cellular phone company representative and ask them to turn off their phone for a short while for, a technical reason, during which the virtual kidnapping is conducted. Thus far virtual kidnappings are most common in America, especially Argentina, Brazil, Columbia and Mexico.

Political Kidnapping: - A kidnapping conducted to extort political concessions from government or security forces. As monetary ransom is no longer enough, it is more difficult to negotiate kidnap victim's freedom as in many cases the political concessions or demands cannot be met by the involved governments, putting the victim's life at greater risk (Dangiwa, 2019).

Bride Kidnapping: - A form of forced marriage in which the groom to be kidnaps his bride. In many cases the would-be couple has never met until the day of the kidnapping. This way of marriage is practiced in the Caucasus region, central Asia, and some nations in Africa. In many cases bride is raped in order to convince her to stay with her husband, as in many traditional cultures the loss of virginity is harshly judged. In some cultures, a bride price is customary, so the kidnapper may contact his victim's family to demand compensation (Dangiwa 2019).

Theoretical Perspectives to Kidnapping

Kidnapping can be seen as false imprisonment in the sense that it involves the illegal confinement of individuals against his or her own will by other individuals in such a way as to violate the confined individual's right to be free from the restraint of movement. This involves taking away of person against the person's will usually to hold the person in false imprisonment or confinement without legal authority. This is often done for ransom or in furtherance of another crime. No one is free from being kidnapped. In Nigeria kidnappers are everywhere targeting both foreigners and non-foreigners alike with little or no resistance from our law enforcement agents. Nigeria security system has been weakened in the face of this confrontation a little has been done to find the socio- economic and underlining factors precipitating this crime.

Several theories have been put forward to explain kidnapping within the Nigerian context. Accordingly, the "economic theory" views kidnapping from economic concept of making ends to meet, (Nseabasi, 2009) has raised the idea that kidnapping is regulated by the laws of demand and supply and is a type of social action that involves the calculation on the most efficient means to the desired ends. Kidnapping is a social enterprise, "kidnappers are businessmen, they just happen to be on the illegal side of it, if you deprive them of the demand then there is not going to be any supply. This is the reason why perpetrators of this crime choose their victims based on their ability to cough out good money.

As kidnapping was first used as a weapon to fight economic and environmental justice in the Niger Delta, The economic motivation was intermittently used as a means to fund and sustain the fight. The beginning of 2007 saw the emergence of various other deviant groups by various names that hide under liberation struggle to commit economic crimes.

Causes of Kidnapping in Nigeria

1. **Unemployment:** - The high unemployment rate in many countries has forced citizens to find other ways to make money and some of those ways are illegal. Kidnapping a rich person can be a lucrative business. A cash – strapped unemployed person may believe that when he kidnaps someone who is rich, he may be able to become rich himself.
2. **Poverty:** - Any person who lives belows \$1.25 dollar a day is living below the poverty line. Poverty can propel people toward crime as a way to make ends meet. Sometimes, a person who is poor might believe that kidnapping or other illegal acts could provide the necessary money to start a new life.
3. **Illiteracy:** - Illiteracy is the inability to read and write. When people know how to read and writes, they can gain the skills they need in order to become educated, get a job and live a productive life. Literacy and education can also be an important foundation upon which to build a deeper understanding of moral judgement and decision. The kidnapping and bombing perpetrated by bandits, and Boko Haram in Nigeria, are caused by illiteracy, at least in part. The leaders of this groups feed their men false information which the men cannot disprove by reading outside sources. Book Haram fighters engage in suicide bombings killings and kidnappings. They are told that if they die while carrying out their mission, they will inherit the kingdom.

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4. **Loss of Social Value:** - Looking at Nigeria today we have mortgaged our culture of respect, love for human lives, hard work, friendliness and receptiveness to strangers in exchange of the western culture and ostentations orientation. This have given birth to the modern and social evil destroying the core value of our society, which is attributed to the rising crimes in different regions to the celebration of fraudsters by leader (Ahmed, 2015).
5. **Greed:** Some people are not contented with what they have and wish they could buy more and more things, whether its fancy clothes, cars, houses, or Jewelry. This kind of persons may turn to crime to make more money. A wicked business man can kidnap his business rival for a large ransom to become richer.
6. **Politics:** - Corrupt politicians may arrange for the kidnapping of their opponents, sometimes they do this so that their opponents will make concessions or change their votes on the issues.
7. **Corruption:** - A society where corruption is rife is likely to experience a high-level kidnapping. The truth is that if a government is corrupt and embezzling public funds, citizens may react by kidnapping those corrupt politicians or their families in attempt to recoup some of the stolen money, (Ahmed, 2015)

Effects or Consequences of Kidnapping in Nigeria

For the victims, there are many negative consequences of kidnapping, they include: -

1. **Psychological Trauma:** - The negative psychological effect of being abducted are huge, especially for a child. Depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress syndrome (PTSD) may last a life time.
2. **Fear and back of Trust:** - in a society where the incidence of kidnapping is high fear limit people lives and actions. They will always more with caution as they do not know who might be the next target. The rich surround themselves with security guards because of their fear of getting kidnapped.
3. **Socio-economic effects or Consequences:** - This include financial gain, some degree of panic, tension, feeling of insecurity and break of citizen's confidence in the government and the political leadership of the country. In some case kidnapping for reasons of revenge, punishment and/or sexual exploitation has social consequences on the health and social relation of the victims, since it can lead to injuries, death of love one's loss, of money or properties and also breaks the societal linkages that leads to societal unrest, as societal members lose confidence on social harmony.
4. **Political Consequence:** - Political consequences of kidnapping include the government spending a lot of time and money in crime combat ensuring its citizens of their safety of their lives and properties. This also hampers and hinders the image of the country in the international domain, as it scares foreigners from investing and this has a lot of consequence on the socio- economic development of the country (Ahmed 2015).

Current Efforts/Measures undertaken by Government to Curb Kidnapping and other Social Crimes in Nigeria

One of the measures taken by government to check kidnapping and other social crime include various joint security operations comprising in military and para- military agencies such as operation sting, Hadin Kai Hadarin Daji, Harbin Kunama, Ayam Kpatuma among others. The mounting of road blocks, markets ban and suspension are also part of military measures to stem the tides of kidnapping and other social crime across the country. Government and other well-meaning Nigerians have also taken steps in mitigating kidnapping by providing palliatives and social safety nets to the youths and other less privileged individuals, like job creation, youth empowerment social investment programs among others are also parts of the measures to alleviate poverty and reduce social crimes like kidnapping in the country. However, the federal government, as part if its measures has instituted amnesty and rehabilitation program to alleviate the suffering of repentant kidnapers, Bako Haram, bandits and the Niger Delta militants (Kankia, 2016). In spite of the above measure taken by government and other critical stakeholders, the rate of kidnapping and other social crime continues to grow exponentially across the length and breadth of all geo-political zones in the country. Consequently, the need to reinvest a proactive and human friendly approach such as inclusiveness of all in its programs peace and security education to tackle the scourge becomes imperative.

Implications of Kidnapping on Nigeria's National Security

Nigeria is a state under perpetual internal security threat from various ethno- religious militias or political insurgents. From a broader perspective, the threat has social economic, political and environmental dimensions. Each of these dimension's singly and conjointly, greatly affects the nations' stability and well- being. Threats to national security can be said to range from the menace of separatist demands, militancy, terrorism, kidnapping, armed robbery and a host of other crimes which has

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negatively affected the security situation of the society, Oli, (2017) kidnapping has over time become endemic in Nigerian society especially in the Niger Delta region, and now affecting almost all north-western states and other parts of the country. It is fast becoming a lucrative alternative to armed robbery and other related offences. The gravity of kidnapping is so intense that it has virtually affected most persons in our society and has grossly undermined the security of the country. Nigerians and non-Nigerians residing in the country live in fear as regards who will be the next kidnap victim since kidnappers' spare no one as far as their motives are actualised. Over the last few years, the wealthy and other income earners have been picked up by kidnappers who only free their victims after payment of ransom. The incident of kidnapping has affected Nigeria's image as a nation abroad. It has also affected Nigeria's attempts to develop a viable tourism industry as visitors are regularly warned by their countries to be wary of coming to Nigeria. Many would be investors have also stayed away for fears of being kidnapped, (Oli, 2017).

Conclusion

The menace of kidnapping, especially for ransom collection is fast gaining momentum in Nigeria. This calls for concern for both the security agencies and the general public in curbing the prevalence of the phenomenon; kidnapping is assumed to be business practice for criminals, who are in kidnapping act for ransom. This has remained one of the greatest drawbacks to investment in Nigeria Nowadays social vices in the form of armed robbery, murder, assassination and recently kidnapping have attained a frightening level in terms of development in the country.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are proffered:

1. The government should provide employment opportunities and vocational training program to adequately equip people especially the youth with appropriate skills for entrepreneurship, so that they can have something because an idle mind is the devils workshop.
2. The government should ensure a fair and better harnessed equitable distribution in resources of the country in order to promote national unity
3. The general population should encourage complete re-orientation away from get rich quick mind-set of the people that wealth acquired should be from a good source, thereby discouraging corruption
4. Appropriate sanction or penalty should be drafted in the constitution to curtail the menace of kidnapping in the country. Thereby culprits should be apprehended and punished accordingly in order to serve as deterrent to others.
5. Telecommunication companies should assist in tracking and determining the location of kidnappers and other criminals by monitoring calls made by the kidnappers to the victims and their families.
6. The use of armed youth groups and thugs by politicians should be totally discouraged and adequate measures should be taken to stop the youths of these groups by the security agencies.
7. Security agencies should strive hard to restore the public trust and confidence so that they can provide them with adequate information, through community policing. All the security agencies should be committed in serving the people at all cost.

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